

Properties of Waveguide based on Pancharatnam-Berry Phase

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Geometric phase in Optics

Conceptualization of Geometric Phase waveguides

What to expect?

- Light is guided only when GP is gained constantly.
- Waveguide is polarization sensitive.
- Waveguide is simulated numerically using FDTD.

Prospects of PBP Waveguide

$w_D = 3\mu\text{m}, \Delta n = 0.2$

- The quasi-mode of the waveguide can be obtained from its effective-index model.

- The quasi-mode of the waveguide becomes highly structured as the potential of the waveguide is increased.

$w_D = 5\mu\text{m}, \Gamma_0 = 15^\circ, \Delta n = 0.2$

- Waveguide is robust for up to 40% change mismatch.

Future Work

- Physical realization of the PBP waveguide by stacking 1D HWP's using nanogratings.
- Integrated optical components for PIC's.

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